

V International Forum on Teacher Education

Training of Future Teachers of the Russian Language as Native and Foreign: Problems and Ways of Overcoming Them

Elena N. Strelchuk*

Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street

Abstract

The study of the Russian language, its distribution, and preservation in many respects depend on specialists in the field of philology, in particular, teachers who are working not only in Russia but also abroad. Currently, the problem of training future teachers of the Russian language as a native and as a foreign language has become relevant. After graduating from the university, students do not want to work according to the profession. The purpose of the study is to reveal the problems associated with the training of future teachers of the Russian language in Russian universities and to determine ways to solve them. For this purpose, several methods were used: complex theoretical analysis, observation, social and pedagogical, basic and diagnostic, pilot pedagogical studies. During the research, more than 300 participants from different countries of the world took part. The problems that are demonstrating why students choose the philological faculty were identified. Then, the motivation to master their future profession disappears. The solutions of problems based on a pedagogical experiment are offered, i.e. development of special courses, testing modern technologies that allow building the process of teaching professional activity taking into account the clip thinking of students and multicultural environment of the University. The conclusions presented in the article aim teachers at the active creative process directed at the development of motivation of students to mastering future profession in the system of higher education of the Russian Federation.

Keywords: Russian language as native; Russian language as foreign; preparation problems; clip consciousness; motivation; polycultural educational environment.

© 2019 Elena N. Strelchuk

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2019 (V International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. Tel.: + 79196415246; e-mail address: elenastrelchuk@mail.ru

Introduction

Significant changes have been taking place in the Russian education system in the last decade. They concern replacements of the leadership (a division of the Ministry of Education and Science into two departments: Ministry of Public Education and Ministry of Science and the Higher Education) and the educational process. Federal state educational standards have changed many times and therefore, the competence approach has become relevant. It involves the formation of a person with a wide range of knowledge, capable of solving complex problems in professional activity, making decisions and their implementation in a multi-polar world. This is not a complete list of changes. There are much more of them, which are directly related to the organization of secondary and higher professional education in general and its individual structures in particular.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to reveal the problems associated with the training of future teachers of the Russian language in Russian universities and to determine ways to solve them.

Literature review

It is natural that considerable changes in Russian education come under the spotlight of not only professionals but also of a wide circle. So, in recent years, more and more often was said that it has become difficult to work in Russian schools and nobody wants to choose a teaching profession. At the same time, teachers define the reasons which influence their work and desire to find another. Among them are listed the insecurity of the teacher and no state support. Also, they are training for the state exams, a huge amount of paperwork, electronic journals, psychological difficulties of modern children, and etc. There is also scientific research helping 'to shed light' on the social status of the teacher in modern society and his preparation for professional activity (Slepenkova, 2007; Kochemasova, 2018).

However, this problem also concerns universities and institutions, and the training of future teachers of the Russian language. Not only Russian but also foreign countries' students are enrolled at philological faculties. Some of them study for free; others study on a contract basis. After graduation, many of them do not want to work as teachers. In this regard, currently, there is an acute problem of training teachers of the Russian language for future professional activities.

It is necessary to tell that the problem was touched upon by modern teachers, scientists, and methodologists more than once. Pedagogical journals publish articles that address the problem we have identified (Zakirova, 2012; Rybakov, 2017). The authors offer their approaches to the study and solutions. However, nobody considers, according to us, one very important fact that not only Russians but also foreign students study at philological faculties at Russian universities. Currently, the multicultural environment of the educational environment has a pronounced specificity: in the process of training, professional skills and abilities are acquired not only by future teachers of Russian as a native language but also as foreign. At the same time, the number of foreigners in relation to Russians is in the ratio: 40% to 60% (on the example of Peoples' Friendship University of Russia).

Therefore, the problem of training of future teachers of Russian gets not only local but also large-scale international character. First of all, it is connected to the distribution of Russian abroad, strengthening of its positions in the global multilingual world. Graduates who return to their homelands to teach Russian become carriers of the Russian culture, mentality, Russian and literature to some extent. As noted by Berditchevski (2016, p. 47) "today the universities are preparing mainly philologists who are poorly

prepared for teaching in a multilingual world", including outside Russia. Though the need for teachers of Russian as foreign increases in certain countries. So, "the analysis of the status and problems of training of teachers of Russian language and Literature in Kyrgyzstan and the implementation process of the competence approach in the higher education learning process has led to the conclusion that recently there has been growing interest and an increased need for training of teachers of Russian language and literature" (Baklanova, 2017, p. 40).

Methodology

The identification of the problems connected with the training of future teachers of Russian as a native and as a foreign language in universities of the Russian Federation and the definition of ways of their decision became a research objective.

To achieve this goal, the following methods were used:

- method of complex theoretical analysis (analysis of scientific literature, normative documents);
- observation method (the continuous and included observation of the process of training of students at philological faculty in the conditions of the language environment);
- social and pedagogical method (analysis of programs, curricula);
- basic and diagnostic method (conversations with teachers, questioning of students);
- method of pilot pedagogical studies.

The Peoples' Friendship University of Russia (RUDN, Moscow) became the main platform for the research. The experiment was conducted in 2016 - 2019. It was attended by over 300 recipients. These are representatives of Russia, China, Vietnam, Hungary, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Ukraine, Venezuela, Cyprus, Uzbekistan, Thailand, Bulgaria, Cameroon, Congo, Chad, Egypt, and many other countries. There were students of 3-4 courses in the direction of preparation 45.03.01 (Philology). In percentage, it looks as follows: 60% – Russians, 40% – foreigners.

At the first stage (2016 - 2017) is search-theoretical. Pedagogical and methodical literature was studied; the analysis of programs and curricula was carried out, observation of the process of training of students at philological faculty in the conditions of the language environment was carried out; questioning of students and a conversation with teachers was carried out, the purpose was proved, research problems were defined.

At the second stage (2017 - 2018) experimental modeling was performed. The ascertaining experiment was developed, the course "practice-Oriented methods of teaching Russian at school" was corrected, and the program of the special course "Professional communication", the educational and experimental materials focused on modern pedagogical technologies and clip consciousness of students were developed.

At the third stage (2018 - 2019) analytical and generalizing was performed. There was the processing of the obtained information, the analysis, generalization, and systematization of results of experimental work.

Results

Russian and foreign students enter the faculty of Philology for the following main reasons:

- love to Russian and Literature;
- the desire of parents;

desire to receive the philologist's profession as one of their widespread professions in the society (only Russians);

the idea of philological faculty as the easiest faculty (only foreigners).

Thus, some students are motivated when entering the faculty of Philology, while others are less motivated. In the process of studying at the University, many students have no motivation to study for their future profession. So, Russian and foreign students named the main reasons:

a small amount of hours for practical training;

the complexity of many disciplines that are not directly related to the future profession and do not cause any interest;

a large number of hours on independent studying of material;

lack of interest in disciplines owing to "weak" supply of material.

At the same time, it should be noted that among difficulties when training at philological faculty foreigners add also:

own laziness;

bad knowledge of the Russian grammar.

In the course of the study, the ways of solving problems aimed at the formation and development of interest in the chosen profession were proposed. It is necessary:

to keep continuity between disciplines and courses within the Federal educational standards of the higher education;

to enter into the educational process the special courses contributing to the formation and the development of motivation to the future profession of students:

take into account the influence of the multicultural environment of the educational process in Russian universities and build the learning process taking into account the principles of differentiation and individualization, allowing to activate the work of foreign students;

to think over the organization of practical training (including the implementation of independent work) with the involvement of various modern pedagogical technologies;

to take into account to feature of clip consciousness of students in this connection to use different types of the exercises and tasks bringing a variety educational process.

Discussions

As you know the professional training of teachers of the Russian language consists of two fundamental components: the theoretical and practical parts Atarshchikova & Ponomarev (2017, p. 37) believes that the practice allows the student to 'know themselves', self-develop, self-determine, 'in order to acquire self-confidence... to engage ...in professional activities'.

Transition to the new Federal educational standards caused changes in educational programs and curricula of higher education institutions of the Russian Federation. There was a reduction of hours on many objects. Baklanova (2017) writes that "if on a specialist programme on teaching discipline "Modern Russian" 500 classroom hours were allotted (as much for independent work) then, in a bachelor degree, we have 340 hours. Independent work increased for 524 hours", hours by a practical training were considerably reduced.

It is supposed that an increase in hours at independent work will allow developing the identity of the student according to the competency-based approach designated in educational standards. "Implementation of educational programs of the third generation predetermines need of change not only content of the training but also approaches to a search of forms of the organization of educational process

in which strengthening of a role and continuous optimization of independent work of students" (Burakova, 2013).

It should be noted that the educational process and earlier attention in the Russian and foreign pedagogics was paid to a role of independent work in process. However, as practice shows, students are not accustomed to independent work. Despite the differences in many educational systems, both foreign and Russian students perform independent work poorly, on the principle of "Just to pass!" The exception is made by some representatives of foreign countries, in particular, graduates of Vietnamese schools, who show diligence in their studies, including when performing independent work.

What is the reason? Why students do not want to get knowledge independently?

Currently, most students use only one source of information – the Internet. Downloaded abstracts, solved problems, read short annotations of literary texts assist in obtaining knowledge, but do not solve the problem – learning to independently search and process the information received. Today's students are not used to working with large sources of information, especially to analyze them and draw any conclusions. As a result, the performance of independent work does not form and develop an interest in a subject, and on the contrary, discharges of it. Therefore, in their questionnaires, students note that they do not like to study at the faculty of Philology, as few hours are allocated for practical classes, lectures are uninteresting, have to work hard on their own.

According to scholars, "the General trend of improving methods and forms of education is to enhance cognitive interests and as much as possible to develop independence of trainees" (Burakova, 2013, p. 99). Special attention should be paid to modern technologies. Thus, Ostanina (2014, p. 69) writes that "modernization of education which actively began in pedagogics of Western Europe and the USA in the 19th century placed particular emphasis on the development of independence and an initiative of students. This principle corresponded to a Waldorf school, Mannheim learning system, the system of the Dalton plan, the teaching techniques by the method of projects, etc."

It is quite possible to agree that the active implementation of modern pedagogical technologies brings a variety of training processes. It is no accident that nowadays many foreign and Russian technologies have become popular in Russian pedagogy. We'll mention just some of them that are actively used in the classroom for language learning: design, games, critical thinking, collaboration, debate, case, web quest.

In fact, it is necessary to establish the fact that students with desire attend lectures where the supply of material is carried out at the high professional level which is supported by the attraction of modern pedagogical technologies including computer. On such occupations and terminology of the studied the subject becomes clear, under a condition if it is displayed on the monitor.

In practical classes, the use of different technologies becomes even more popular. A simple conversation on a specific topic is no longer interesting to anyone. Students are waiting for a lot of information that would make the lesson useful and rich. "Change of scenery" is what has now become relevant, has become of paramount importance.

In this regard, the question of the clip consciousness of the modern generation arises acutely. Frequent change of activity in the classroom, a variety of forms and techniques – this is what the modern student is focused on.

There are different points of view regarding clip consciousness and its role in the educational process. Some scientists believe that "guided by the installation on the simplification of information, the media managed to deeply distort the mental abilities of Russians, so if you do not start to fight this, the

system will pass the point of bifurcation, and again create a "thinking man" will be much more difficult" (Dokuka, 2013, p. 177).

Other Russian scientists hold a different point of view. "What are the features of clip thinking it is necessary to consider teachers in modeling lessons? Carriers of clip thinking do not perceive information homogeneous in content and relative in the way of presentation (a long explanation of the teacher, reading large articles and books). They require brevity, imagery, fragmentation information, and frequent changes in its sources and activities" (Semenovskikh, 2014, p. 3).

Indeed, you can talk for a long time about the advantages and disadvantages of clip consciousness but you cannot ignore it in the educational process. On the example of disciplines "Practice-oriented methods of teaching Russian at school" and "Professional communication" we have considered and tested modern pedagogical technologies that allow building the process of teaching philologists-students taking into account the features of clip consciousness.

The discipline "Practice-oriented methods of teaching Russian at school" is practical training and is conducted in a multicultural environment in which students come from around the world. A distinctive feature of the discipline is that it is intended for Russian students who have to seize a technique of teaching Russian at school. The discipline does not attract any interest as hardly they will be able to teach Russian at the Russian schools of foreign students. Respectively the motivation, in this case, comes down to zero.

Taking into account the designated factors of training process which were based on the principles of differentiation and identity were organized. Throughout the course (both semesters in the 3rd year) Russian and foreign students performed different tasks. So, if Russians wrote an essay about the role of the unified state exam in the life of schoolchildren, foreign students wrote an essay about the exam in Russian as a foreign language for passing and obtaining a Certificate. It should be noted that after discussing the written work performed during the discussion, it turned out that both Russian and foreign students were interested in learning about the exams they took, the information was useful and informative.

Most of the lessons of the discipline "practice-Oriented methods of teaching Russian at school" were built with the involvement of various pedagogical technologies. Among them:

- Technology of cooperation
- Design technology
- Technology of critical thinking
- Game technology

Without stopping specifically on every technology we will note that different types of technologies replaced each other. Thus, during one activity foreign students presented material about the development of education in the country (design technology). Russian students analyzed textbooks on the Russian language, which were used in schools of the Russian Federation in the past and present, put forward for discussion their proposals on the appropriateness of the use of certain exercises (critical thinking technology). Application of different technologies made the process of training various (including independent work), directed to change of information, the emphasis of attention on its figurativeness and brevity that is peculiar to clip consciousness.

Between disciplines and courses, the principle of continuity is one of the major all-didactic principles have to remain. In Russian universities introduced elective courses, which are a kind of help for those students who are not well mastered the discipline of the base part. For example, at Perm State University of Humanities and education "discipline "Modern Russian language" supports the discipline of choice "Problematic issues of the modern Russian language" (Baklanova, 2017, p. 42).

In Peoples' Friendship University of Russia specialization courses are for choice entered for the purpose of development of motivation to the future professional activity of students. Thus, we have developed a special course "Professional communication" in the amount of 36 hours of classroom hours. It is intended for foreign students of the 4th year and is a kind of continuation of the discipline "Practice-oriented methods of teaching Russian at school" but in a slightly different perspective. Its main goal is to develop a person capable of professional communication in the modern multilingual world. The objectives of the course include:

- acquaintance to the basic concepts of discipline;
- drawing up texts in the field of professional communication;
- analytical studying and assessment of samples of the professional speech;
- development of the practical abilities necessary for the establishment of interpersonal contact in the professional sphere of communication;
- increase in the level of speech culture of the teacher in oral and written communication.

During lessons, foreign students performed tasks of different difficulty and complexity. They were helped by modern pedagogical technologies. In particular, they made projects on the subjects "The Teacher in My Country", "Russian – It Is Difficult, but It Is Interesting" (design technology). They carried out questionnaires among fellow students on the subject "My Profession – My Future", analyzed the received results and made out them as reports in writing (technology of critical thinking).

Held a competition of speakers in the subject "The Teacher – It Sounds Proud!" The performance was estimated by the following criteria: normative, logicity, expressiveness, accuracy, relevance, wealth. The designated criteria allowed to improve knowledge of Russian contributed to the development of interest in the chosen profession.

During this special course, we not only focused on the clip thinking of students but also did not forget "about the positive experience of training future teachers, accumulated by more than one generation of teachers" (Zakirova, 2012, p. 33). We fully share the point of view of Rybakov (2017, p. 232) who says that "the pursuit of innovation, natural in the field of technological development, is inappropriately transferred to the field of Philology..." To this end, we proposed the implementation of traditional tasks, for example, such as working with scientific sources. Here are examples of tasks.

Task №1. Read the article of the famous Russian scientist Shchukin (2012) "A competence and competent approach to the language teaching" (the journal "Research and development. Modern communication studies". 2012. Vol. 1. No. 1. C. 36-38 [Http://nauka.infa-m.ru/journal/vien/sovremennaya-kommunikativistika](http://nauka.infa-m.ru/journal/vien/sovremennaya-kommunikativistika)). Make an oral report about what is the difference between the concepts "competence" and "competence".

Task №2. Express your opinion on the following thesis: "It is known that the speech of the teacher includes, first of all, art to speak, address human heart. Prove that so if you agree. Disprove if this opinion does not coincide with yours".

Tasks had different characters, but all of them were aimed at the development of motivation to mastering the future profession of the philologist, in our case of the teacher of Russian.

Conclusion

The world of digital technologies is making fundamental changes in the minds of modern students, focused on the fragmentary and figurative information, frequency and changeability. Future

teachers of the Russian language are a kind of "carriers" of clip thinking. As a result, the organization of the educational process should take into account their psychological characteristics, develop special courses and apply modern pedagogical technologies in the classroom in the multicultural environment of the Russian University. Such approach allows speeding up work of students, forms an interest in professional activity, contributes to the development of motivation, from which teachers will be trained by the higher Russian school, the future of Russian, its international status and prevalence in different corners of the globe in many respects depends on it.

References

- Atarshchikova, E. N., & Ponomarev, E. G. (2017). Practices in the pedagogical institute as a means of professional adaptation of the teacher. *Collection of scientific articles*, 36-40.
- Baklanova, I. I. (2017). The successive connection of optional disciplines with basic courses as the factor of teacher-philologist preparation quality improvement. *Collection of scientific articles. Training of the teacher of Russian in the system of high school education: problems and prospects*, 40-42.
- Berditchevski, A. L. (2016). The system of specialists for Russian as a foreign language in the 21st century: problems and prospects. *Russian Language and Culture Reflected in Translation*, 1, 44-54.
- Burakova, G. J. (2013). Bachelors' Out-of-Class Work in Conditions of Implementation of New Standards of Education (on the example of studying "Elementary Mathematics"). *Yaroslavl pedagogical bulletin. Psychology and pedagogical sciences*, 2, 95-100.
- Dokuka, S. V. (2013). Clip thinking as phenomenon of information society. *Social sciences and present*, 2, 175-180.
- Kochemasova, L. A. (2018). The social status of teachers in modern teacher education. *Education and self-development*, 3, 66-77.
- Ostanina, S. A. (2014). The organization of independent work of students of creative higher education institutions in the conditions of realization of FGOS VPO of the third generation. *News of the Volgograd state pedagogical university*, 6(91), 68-73.
- Rybakov, M. A. (2017). The preparation of philologists problems and outlooks in condition of new standard permanent implantation. *Collection of scientific articles*, 231- 233.
- Shchukin, A. A. (2012). A competence and competent approach to the language teaching. Research and development. *Modern communication studies*, 1(1), p. 36-38.
- Semenovskikh, T. V. (2014). Fenomen of "clip thinking" in the educational high school environment. *Online magazine Naukovedeniye*, 5(24), 1-15.
- Slepenkova, E. A. (2007). Pedagogical research activity in vocational training of the teacher of domestic school in the 20th century: what did change in 100 years? *Issues of education*, 1, 94-108.
- Zakirova, R.Y. (2012). Current problems of training of the teacher of Russian in the system of higher education. *Kazan pedagogical magazine*, 2(92), 31-36